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1 ~~Understanding Palaeoecological differences underlie the~~ rare co-occurrence of Miocene

2 European primates ~~based on musk deer evolutionary palaeoecology~~

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4 Daniel DeMiguel^{1,2,*}, Laura Domingo^{3,4}, Israel M. Sánchez², Isaac Casanovas-Vilar², Josep

5 M. Robles² & David M. Alba²

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7 ¹ARAID / Universidad de Zaragoza. Departamento de Ciencias de la Tierra, Área de

8 Paleontología. Pedro Cerbuna 12, 50009 Zaragoza, Spain; ²Institut Català de Paleontologia

9 Miquel Crusafont, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Edifici ICTA-ICP, C/ Columnes s/n,

10 Campus de la UAB, 08193 Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain; ³Departamento de

11 Geodinámica, Estratigrafía y Paleontología Facultad de Ciencias Geológicas, Universidad

12 Complutense de Madrid, José Antonio Novais 12, 28040, Madrid, Spain; ⁴Earth and Planetary

13 Sciences Department. University of California Santa Cruz, 1156 Hight Street, 95064, Santa

14 Cruz, California, United States of America.

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16 *Corresponding author

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18 **Abstract**

19 **Background:** The two main primate groups recorded throughout the European Miocene,
20 hominoids and pliopithecoids, seldom co-occur. Due to both their rarity and insufficiently
21 understood palaeoecology, it is currently unclear whether the infrequent co-occurrence of
22 these groups is due to sampling bias or reflects different ecological preferences. Here we rely
23 on the densely sampled primate-bearing sequence of Abocador de Can Mata (ACM) in Spain
24 to test whether turnovers in primate assemblages are correlated with palaeoenvironmental
25 changes. We reconstruct dietary evolution through time (ca. 12.6–11.4 Ma), and hence
26 climate and habitat, using tooth-wear patterns and carbon and oxygen isotope compositions of
27 enamel of the ubiquitous musk-deer *Micromeryx*.

28 **Results:** Our results reveal that primate species composition is strongly correlated with
29 distinct environmental phases. Large-bodied hominoids (dryopithecines) are recorded in
30 humid, densely-forested environments on the lowermost portion of the ACM sequence. In
31 contrast, pliopithecoids inhabited less humid, patchy ecosystems, being replaced by
32 dryopithecines and the small-bodied *Pliobates* toward the top of the series in gallery forests
33 embedded in mosaic environments.

34 **Conclusions:** These results ~~contradict previous inferences~~support the view that pliopithecoid
35 primates preferred ~~more~~less humid habitats than hominoids, and reveal that differences in
36 behavioural ecology were the main factor underpinning their rare co-occurrence during the
37 European Miocene. ~~Our F~~findings further support that ACM hominoids, like ~~other~~-Miocene
38 apes as a whole, inhabited more seasonal environments than extant apes. Finally, and this
39 study highlights the importance of high-resolution, local investigations to complement larger-
40 scale analyses and illustrates that continuous and densely-sampled fossiliferous sequences are
41 essential for deciphering the complex interplay between biotic and abiotic factors that shaped
42 past diversity.

44 **Keywords:** hominoids, pliopithecoids, primate evolution/adaptation, palaeodiet, stable
45 isotopes, tooth wear, feeding behaviour, palaeobiology

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46 **Background**

47 Fossil primates from the Miocene of Europe are generally rare and absent from most sites,
48 and, when recorded, different primate species only seldom co-occur within a single locality
49 (stratigraphic horizon). As a result, there is an ongoing debate about the factors underpinning
50 the geographic and chronostratigraphic distribution of Miocene primates in this continent [1-
51 6]. Before the dispersal of cercopithecoids (Old World monkeys) into Europe by the early
52 Turolian (ca. 8.5 Ma, late Miocene), two main groups are recorded there: pliopithecoids,
53 generally considered a Eurasian clade of stem catarrhines (i.e., preceding the cercopithecoid-
54 hominoid split [7]); and hominoids (crown catarrhines more closely related to extant apes and
55 humans than to cercopithecoids [8-10]). Both groups presumably dispersed from Africa to
56 Eurasia following the closure of the Tethys Seaway during the late middle Miocene, and
57 subsequently diversified across the continent giving rise to multiple genera and species. There
58 are approximately one hundred known localities recording either or both of these groups—
59 almost 20% corresponding to Abocador de Can Mata (ACM) in Spain—, although they only
60 co-occur in less than 10% of them, with pliopithecoid-bearing localities being slightly more
61 abundant (ca. 55 vs. 45%) than hominoid-bearing ones [4,5]. European hominoids are
62 generally larger than pliopithecoids and considered great apes (hominids), except for the
63 small-bodied *Pliobates*, interpreted as a stem hominoid [11].

64 There are very few sites in the European Miocene where hominoids and pliopithecoids co-
65 occur [1,4,5] and, in most cases, fossils of each group come from different localities within
66 the same site (e.g., different karstic fissure fillings from La Grive) or it is uncertain whether
67 their remains came from the same stratigraphic horizon (e.g., Castell de Barberà [6]). Strong
68 taphonomic evidence supporting sympatry is only available from Rudabánya in Hungary [12]
69 and ACM (locality ACM/C5-C3 [5]). These localities therefore offer a unique opportunity to
70 evaluate the palaeoenvironmental conditions that enabled the coexistence of pliopithecoids
71 and hominoids. Given the rarity of primate remains among mammalian assemblages from the
72 European Miocene, the infrequent co-occurrence of two different primate species at a single
73 locality might be, at least in part, a sampling artifact [1]. However, the lack of co-occurrence

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7 74 in many well-sampled primate-bearing localities would rather support the view that their
8 75 infrequent coexistence is a real phenomenon that requires an explanation.

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10 76 The competitive exclusion principle [13] predicts that species occupying the same
11 77 ecological niche cannot coexist on the long-term, ultimately leading to the prevalence of one
12 78 over the other, or to the progressive divergence of their respective niches. This explanation is
13 79 unlikely to hold for different clades such as pliopithecoids and hominoids, characterised
14 80 among others by different locomotor adaptations—leading to the proposal that these two
15 81 groups probably had different habitat preferences, which only enabled their coexistence under
16 82 particular ecological conditions [1]. Early ecomorphological analyses based on ungulate
17 83 hypsodonty (a proxy for vegetation structure also used to infer palaeoprecipitation) have
18 84 concluded that both hominoid and pliopithecoid-bearing localities from the European
19 85 Miocene were more humid than those lacking primates [2]. More recent work based on
20 86 hypsodonty further showed that pliopithecoids generally inhabited more humid environments
21 87 (i.e., with higher moisture and/or rainfall) than hominoids, although probably less humid than
22 88 those in which both groups co-occur [4]. However, given the small number of fossil localities
23 89 recording both taxa, such comparisons lack statistical power and may fail to consider
24 90 palaeoenvironmental differences across geography and time throughout the Miocene,
25 91 especially at the regional and local scales.

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38 92 Focusing on ~~faunal elements that the accompanying primates fauna~~ within a single area
39 93 and ~~throughout over~~ a restricted time span would ~~considerably reduce such potential biases~~
40 94 ~~and~~ allow us to test whether turnovers in the primate assemblage are correlated to local
41 95 changes in palaeoenvironmental conditions. The composite stratigraphic sequence of ACM,
42 96 located in the area of els Hostalets de Pierola within the Vallès-Penedès Basin (NE Iberian
43 97 Peninsula [14]) (Fig. 1a-c), and spanning more than 1 Myr (12.6–11.4 Ma [5,15]), offers an
44 98 unparalleled opportunity to test this hypothesis for several reasons. First, the ACM sequence
45 99 has delivered one of the most diverse primate assemblages from the European Miocene,
46 100 including both hominoids and pliopithecoids [5]. Second, the co-occurrence of hominoids and
47 101 pliopithecoids has only been recorded in one out of the 19 ACM primate-bearing localities,

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7 102 and the distribution of each group throughout the series does not appear random [5]. Finally,
8 103 thanks to continuous palaeontological surveillance during the construction of a landfill, most
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10 104 of the fossil finds are accurately dated based on detailed litho-, bio- and magnetostratigraphic
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12 105 correlations [5,16,17]. This offers the opportunity to test alternative explanations for the
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14 106 ~~inhomogeneous-variable~~ temporal distribution of both primate groups during a restricted time
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16 107 span and within an uniform depositional setting.

17 108 With this aim in mind, here we present a reconstruction of the local climate and
18
19 109 palaeoenvironments through the ACM sequence based on tooth wear and dental enamel stable
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21 110 carbon and oxygen isotope values (represented by the notation $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of the ruminant
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23 111 *Micromeryx*—(Fig. 1d and Fig S1)—a representative of the family Moschidae (musk-deer)
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25 112 [18,19]. Because ~~the~~ diet of any plant-eating mammal is a direct link with the habitats in
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27 113 ~~where-which~~ it lives, we used the diet (i.e., ecology) of this ruminant to inform about ACM
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29 114 primate ecological preferences and habitats. The selection of *Micromeryx* is based on the
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31 115 following reasons: (1) the record of this taxon throughout the ACM stratigraphic sequence,
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33 116 characterised by abundant isolated teeth and dentognathic fragments, allows us to construct a
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35 117 continuous tooth-wear and isotopic record; (2) by focusing on a single genus, we can
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37 118 characterise more consistently changes in the vegetation cover, food abrasiveness, etc. across
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39 119 the selected time interval, avoiding thus biases due to different physiologies; and (3)
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41 120 *Micromeryx* was ubiquitous in the Miocene of Iberia, inhabiting a varied range of biomes
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43 121 from more or less open savannas to (sub)tropical forests [18,20], and exhibiting an
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45 122 extraordinary versatility in terms of exploitation of nutrients and resources. The combination
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47 123 of all these factors justifies the suitability of employing *Micromeryx* as a case study to
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49 124 investigate the environmental and climatic shifts that took place during the latest middle
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51 125 Miocene in the area of els Hostalets de Pierola.

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53 127 **Results**

54 128 **Tooth wear**

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7 130 The fossil material studied consists of dentognathic remains and isolated teeth of *Micromeryx*.
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9 131 Although initially a single species of *Micromerys* was reported from ACM [15], the currently
10 132 available dental material indicates the presence of three different morphotypes that likely
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12 133 represent different species (Supplementary Note 1).
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14 134 For mesowear we measured individuals and provide the results for the three morphotypes
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16 135 separately (Supplementary Note 2). All *Micromeryx* morphotypes (Table 1) show occlusal
17 136 surfaces with predominance of high relief (pH = 95–100%) and sharpened cusps (pS = 69–
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19 137 87%), although there is a considerable proportion of rounded apices (pR = 13–31%).
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21 138 Morphotypes do not have any incidence of blunt cusps or, except for *Micromeryx* morphotype
22 139 3 (pL = 5%), low occlusal relief (which relates to a low height difference between tooth cusps
23
24 140 and valleys). Average mesowear score (MS) for morphotypes ranges from 0.19 to 0.31 (Table
25
26 141 1). We do find significant differences with the chi-square test (χ^2) but marginally non-
27 142 significant with the Fisher's exact test. For the chi-square test, the results show that
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29 143 *Micromeryx* morphotype 1 is ~~reported~~ different from morphotype 2 (p = 0,0283), whereas
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31 144 non-significant differences are between morphotypes 2 and 3 (p = 0,2255) and between
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33 145 morphotypes 1 and 3 (p = 0,2019). On average, mesowear results indicate a browsing on soft
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35 146 vegetation and low levels of abrasives (endogenous phytolith-rich grasses and
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37 147 dicotyledonous, and exogenous dust and grit), although *Micromeryx* morphotype 1—with
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39 148 more rounded cusps and higher MS (Table 1)—shows a shift toward the exploitation of
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41 149 tougher and more abrasive foods than the others.

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43 151 **Stable isotope data**
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45 152 The difference between carbonate ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$) and phosphate ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$) oxygen isotopic
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47 153 composition ~~is useful~~ can be used to monitor possible bioapatite diagenetic alteration.
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49 154 *Micromeryx* tooth enamel did not undergo extensive post-burial alteration since the difference
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51 155 calculated between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ ($\Delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3\text{-PO}_4} = \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3} - \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$) values for the
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7 156 whole dataset ($8.6 \pm 0.8\%$) is within the range obtained when considering modern mammals
8 157 ($\sim 8.6\text{--}9.1\%$ [21,22]) (Supplementary Note 3).

10 158 *Micromeryx* morphotypes (Table 1 and Table S1) yielded tooth enamel $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values
11 159 indicative of woodland to woodland-mesic C_3 grassland conditions (see Supplementary Note
12 160 4 for a detailed explanation of the calculated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ cut-off values among different habitats).
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14 161 Significant differences in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values have been only found between morphotypes 1 and 2 of
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16 162 *Micromeryx* ($t = 4.250$, $p < 0.001$) (Table S2). Tooth enamel $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values do
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18 163 not show significant differences among the three morphotypes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$: $F = 0.845$, $df = 2$, $p =$
19 164 0.439 and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$: $F = 0.562$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.577$) (Table S2).

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23 166 **Relationship between mesowear and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values**
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25 167 A scatter plot showing the correlation between mean MS and mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB) among
26 168 *Micromeryx* morphotypes by localities was constructed (Fig. 2). Niche domains are visually
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28 169 presented for each variable. This approach (described in Supplementary Notes 2 and 4)
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30 170 allowed us to contextualise the niche occupation per morphotype and locality given the
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32 171 variables investigated. MS and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values point to a frequent ingestion of C_3 plants in
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34 172 woodland to mesic C_3 grasslands. Mean MS of some individuals of morphotypes 1 and 2
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36 173 from a few localities (those with $\text{MS} = 0.33$ to 0.5) is also compatible with ~~+~~regular
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38 174 consumption of C_4 vegetation. C_4 plants have never been documented as an important
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40 175 component of plant communities in the Iberian Neogene (despite being recorded there since
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42 176 the Oligocene) [23, 24]. However, they may well have been present to some extent in some
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44 177 areas and/or time intervals (e.g., ACM/C4-C1 and ACM/C5-C2 at ~ 11.8 Ma).

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47 179 **Discussion**
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49 180 ***Micromeryx* diet at ACM**
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51 181 Our results indicate that the bulk of *Micromeryx* diet at ACM consisted of foliage with a
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53 182 particular emphasis on forbs, dicots and woody leaves. The various morphotypes generally

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7 183 maintain sharpened, high-relief cusp apices and low MS—a signal that informs that foods
8 184 were of relatively low abrasion, as seen in extant forest-dweller browsers [25]. We rule out a
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10 185 regular consumption of fruits and/or seeds in ACM, as teeth show no signs of strong rounding
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12 186 or blunt apices—and frugivorous taxa have significant percentages of rounded and blunt
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14 187 cusps because of tip-crushing [26]. These results contrast with some previous data for middle
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16 188 and late Miocene *Micromeryx* from elsewhere in Europe, which appear strictly frugivorous
17 189 [~~27-29~~], ~~albeit with a different degree of frugivory [29]~~. However, these results are in
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19 190 agreement with the leaf browsing inferred for other *Micromeryx* [28,30]. Therefore, it seems
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21 191 that *Micromeryx*, since its oldest occurrences in the middle Miocene of Eurasia, was capable
22 192 ~~to~~ of feeding alternatively on fruits, ~~/~~seeds ~~or~~ and soft leaves, depending on habitat-specific
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24 193 circumstances (e.g., ecologic niche partitioning or food availability). In the case of ACM, the
25
26 194 unusual secondary crests of the upper molars of *Micromeryx* are compatible with an
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28 195 adaptation for heavier reliance on leaves and stems, as seen in other mammalian groups
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30 196 [31]—an anatomical trait that is consistent with the folivorous signal retrieved from
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32 197 mesowear analyses. The *Micromeryx* from ACM are therefore the only ones in which these
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34 198 features are recognised, probably showing a regional adaptation associated with the
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36 199 particularity of these environments. Moreover, *Micromeryx* had a wider dietary plasticity than
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38 200 modern *Moschus*, whose diet comprises mainly arboreal lichens (a resource rarely exploited
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40 201 by other ruminants), forbs and woody leaves [32].

41 202 Within such a generalised soft, leafy browsing, there are differences among morphotypes
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43 203 in tooth wear and isotopic values through time (Table S1). In other words, the same
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45 204 morphotype behaves differently when the temporal gradient is considered. The less sharp and
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47 205 more rounded cusps of *Micromeryx* morphotypes 1 and 2 recorded from 11.81 Ma onwards
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49 206 (and a signal of browse-dominated mixed feeding for some individuals) reflect a more
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51 207 pronounced abrasion than in older specimens, and indicate that more abrasive browse and/or
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53 208 some dust/grit-infested foliage was eaten—as extant browsers that feed on leafy, soft foods
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55 209 generally maintain sharpened/high relief cusps [26,30] (Table S1). That is, abrasive browse
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57 210 and encroachments by exogenous dust/grit content was only slight or even absent in the diet

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7 211 of older *Micromeryx*, whereas it significantly increased in later forms along the ACM
8 212 sequence. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data support dietary inferences based on mesowear, as all *Micromeryx*
9 213 morphotypes depict values that are within woodland to woodland-mesic C_3 grassland
10 214 conditions, thereby indicating a consumption of both soft leaves and more abrasive grasses.
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16 216 **Temporal patterns in *Micromeryx* tooth wear and stable isotopes along the ACM**
17 217 **sequence**

18 218 The primate assemblage recorded at ACM [5] includes three great ape (dryopithecine) species
19 219 from different genera (*Pierolapithecus catalaunicus*, *Anoiapithecus brevirostris*, and
20 220 *Dryopithecus fontani*) [5,10,16,33,34], the pliopithecoid *Pliopithecus canmatensis* [35],
21 221 probably a second pliopithecoid unassigned to species [36], and a putative stem hominoid
22 222 (*Pliobates cataloniae*) [11], alternatively interpreted as a pliopithecoid [37]. The distribution
23 223 of these taxa is not homogeneous along the ACM sequence, with *Pliopithecus* postdating
24 224 most great ape finds but preceding *Pliobates* [5] (Fig. 3a).

25 225 We show mesowear and isotopic data of *Micromeryx* teeth in chronological order of the
26 226 localities for a time span ranging from 12.38 Ma to 11.63 Ma (Fig. 3), to compare their
27 227 chronostratigraphic distribution with palaeoenvironmental changes through time. While
28 228 remaining within a browsing dietary category based on C_3 plants, differences observed in
29 229 both mesowear and isotopic values among *Micromeryx* specimens provide insight on the
30 230 environmental changes along the ACM temporal sequence during the latest middle Miocene.

31 231 This is particularly relevant given that the lack of other palaeoenvironmental proxies from
32 232 this area (such as pollen or macroplant remains) hinders a more precise reconstruction of the
33 233 vegetation structure and other characteristics of the various habitats occupied by primates.

34 234 Overall, the data reported here indicate that ACM habitats became progressively less
35 235 humid and more heterogeneous (or, at least, are characterised by a gradient towards less dense
36 236 canopy structure and more open patches), as reflected by *i*) a trend toward higher values of
37 237 mesowear—from the sharpest cusps and low MS of 0 at 12.38 Ma (ACM/C1-Ee) to more
38 238 intermediate (more rounded) cusp morphologies and higher MS around 0.5 at 11.60 Ma

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7 239 (ACM/C5-D1) (Fig. 3b); *ii*) an increase in mean *Micromeryx* $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (from -12.4‰ in
8 240 ACM/C1-Ee to -11.1‰ in ACM/C5-D1; Fig. 3c); and *iii*) a high variability in the type of
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10 241 vegetation consumed—revealed by a wider range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in the youngest localities and
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12 242 fuelled by the coexistence of the three morphotypes (see a change in standard deviation
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14 243 values in Table 1). The increase in mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values may have been driven by two
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16 244 phenomena: a shift toward drier habitats, including non-forest patches, or, alternatively, a
17 245 greater reliance on fruits through time. A change toward a more frugivorous diet would have
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19 246 led to a progressive-slight increase in *Micromeryx* tooth enamel $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, as a significant
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21 247 consumption of fruits ultimately results in higher bioapatite $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values [38,39]. There is,
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23 248 however, little reason to support strong frugivory for ACM *Micromeryx*, as this is
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25 249 contradicted by their attrition-dominated mesowear patterns. This does not entail-mean that
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27 250 fruits were unavailable at ACM. In fact, all of the primate species recorded relied on
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29 251 frugivory to a large extent, even if with a different emphasis on hard-object feeding
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31 252 depending on the species [11,40,41]. However, a drop in the estimated Mean Annual
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33 253 Precipitation (MAP) values throughout the sequence (from ~1395 to ~762 mm/yr or from
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35 254 ~1097 to ~575 mm/yr with altitude and latitude correction; Table 1, Fig. 3c, Table S1)
36
37 255 supports the fact that fruits were preferentially exploited by arboreal, or at least
38
39 256 semiterrestrial, species instead of terrestrial taxa such as *Micromeryx*.

40 257 Although the oxygen isotope composition does not vary significantly through time, there
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42 258 is a slight decrease in both $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values (from -28.8‰ and 20.3‰ in
43
44 259 ACM/C1-Ee to 27.4‰ and 18.7‰ in ACM/C5-D1; Fig. 3c, d). Oxygen isotope composition
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46 260 of carbonate ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$) and phosphate ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$) fractions of tooth enamel reflects $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of
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48 261 body water ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{bw}}$) [42,43]. Changes associated with $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{bw}}$ value mirror variations in the
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50 262 isotopic composition of ingested water, either through drinking or plant water (in the case of
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52 263 herbivores). *Micromeryx* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values are less likely to vary according to physiological factors
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54 264 like fractionated water loss through the lungs or skin, since this is a relatively mesic
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56 265 environment overall, and the species are closely related over a narrow time window. When

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7 266 considering extinct mammals such as *Micromeryx*, it is difficult to assess the type of water
8 267 economy they may have had, due to the lack of modern analogues. The extant sister group of
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10 268 *Micromeryx* within the Moschidae is the genus *Moschus* (musk deer) [44], which inhabits
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12 269 forest and mountainous parts of Asia [32,45] and has a browsing diet, although it also has the
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14 270 ability to cope with poorer, less nutritious foods when high quality forage is in short supply,
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16 271 such as in winter [32,46]. Independently from its dietary behaviour, *Moschus* has been
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18 272 observed to drink water on a daily basis (Prikhod'ko, pers. comm.); therefore, its tooth enamel
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20 273 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal will largely be dependent on drinking water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. On the assumption that
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22 274 the water reliance of *Moschus* is applicable to *Micromeryx*, Mean Annual Temperature
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24 275 (MAT) values have been estimated based on *Micromeryx* tooth enamel $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values. They
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26 276 show a decreasing trend along the ACM sequence from 21.4 °C in ACM/C1-Ee to 17.4 °C in
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28 277 ACM/C5-D1 (Table 1, Fig. 3d, Table S1). This trend toward lower temperatures may be
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30 278 framed within the gradual cooling that started by 14 Ma after the Mid-Miocene Climatic
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32 279 Optimum [47]. In the Iberian Peninsula, this long interval, which coincided with the
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34 280 expansion of mesothermic deciduous vegetation and the extinction or significant decrease in
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36 281 abundance of thermophilous evergreen plants [48,49], witnessed an increase in the diversity
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38 282 of moschids [18].

36 283

38 284 **Primate assemblage composition in relation to palaeoenvironmental changes**

39 285 Our analyses further show a fluctuation in diet composition for *Micromeryx* individuals,
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41 286 revealing the existence of three distinct environmental phases in ACM (Table 1, Fig. 3a-d),
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43 287 with temporal patterns in precipitation, temperature and aridity that relate to changes in
44
45 288 primate assemblage composition.

46 289 Phase I — A first phase ranges from the beginning of the sequence (12.38 Ma, ACM/C1-
47
48 290 Ee) to ~11.95 Ma (ACM/C4-Cp), where only *Micromeryx* morphotype 2 is recorded. Overall,
49
50 291 *Micromeryx* maintained sharp apices, high-relief cusp and low average MS of 0.1, and tooth
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52 292 enamel $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of -12.0 ± 0.3 ‰ (VPDB) (Table 1) that point to the consumption of plant

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7 293 resources from relatively dense wooded areas (see Supplementary Note 4 for explanation of
8
9 294 the calculated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ cut-off values among different habitats). Estimated MAP ranges from 928
10 295 to 1190 mm/yr (depending on whether a correction for altitude and latitude is applied or not)
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12 296 (Table 1). In Phase I, *Micromeryx* tooth enamel $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values are the highest
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14 297 among the three environmental phases, with calculated MAT values reaching 21.8 °C (Table
15
16 298 1). According to Whittaker's biome classification [50], estimated MAP and MAT for phase I
17 299 would correspond to those of a tropical seasonal forest/savanna (Fig. S4). This agrees with the
18
19 300 soft-leafy browsing diet inferred from mesowear and indicates a humid climate with rainfall
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21 301 seasonality (although not marked) and the development of long-standing forests with bushy
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23 302 and woody vegetation [22,30,51]. This type of environment at the beginning of the ACM
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25 303 series, characterised by humid and warm forests with a dense upper canopy, is somewhat
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27 304 more seasonal than previous inferences for ACM as a whole [52] and would be suitable for
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29 305 the multiple large-bodied hominoids—*A. brevirostris*, *D. fontani* and *P. catalaunicus*—
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31 306 recorded during phase I. The abundance of trees may have allowed hominoids to eat a diverse
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33 307 array of vegetation, ranging from leaves and soft fruits (*Anoiapithecus* and *Dryopithecus*) to
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35 308 harder and brittle fruits (*Pierolapithecus*) [11,41]. This also fits with the postcranial
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37 309 morphology of *Pierolapithecus*, which indicates an orthograde bodyplan with adaptations for
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39 310 arboreal vertical climbing [10,33,53,54]. Only a single *Micromeryx* specimen from ACM/C2-
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41 311 A3 (IPS29396) displays more rounded cusps and slightly higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. This
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43 312 specimen might reflect the exploitation of more abrasive elements probably located along less
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45 313 humid—but still forested—patches in specific localities. It is noteworthy that only one
46
47 314 pliopithecoid is recorded in this first phase (Fig. 3a) (Pliopithecoida indet. from ACM/C3-B2
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49 315 at 12.06 Ma). ~~Although more data would be required to confirm this, the lack of hominoids
316 between 12.3 and 12.1 Ma might be related to the less humid conditions recorded during this
317 interval. Although they must have been present in more or less distant, more suitable
318 environments) until they become more abundant at 12.0–11.9 [5].~~ This immediately precedes
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51 319 a first short pulse of decreased humidity as documented by ACM/C2-A3, which might
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7 320 explain the lack of great ape record between their first appearance in the sequence at 12.4–
8 321 12.3 and their more abundant record at 12.0–11.9 [5]. This shifting climatic pattern at 11.98
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10 322 Ma towards less humid conditions might have also influenced (preferred) food availability (as
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12 323 seen in *Micromeryx*) and impelled hominoids to exploit alternative sources, especially as
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14 324 fallback foods [41], not consumed before.

15 325 Phase II — ACM localities experienced a different environmental phase from ~11.90 to
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17 326 11.79 Ma. There was a rapid increase in *Micromeryx* phenotypic diversity and population
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19 327 abundance after ACM/C3-Ak (11.88 Ma), with the first co-occurrence of all morphotypes (at
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21 328 least three) being recorded at ACM/C4-C1 (Fig. 3b-d). Compared to phase I, from 11.88 Ma
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23 329 onwards the less sharp and more rounded cusp shapes, higher average MS of 0.16 of
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25 330 *Micromeryx* and the increase in the mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (-11.4 ± 1.2 ‰, VPDB) (Table 1, Fig. 3b, c)
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27 331 are consistent with less humid and more open areas during this part of the ACM sequence.
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29 332 The broader range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ observed in phase II (Fig. 3c) is congruent with a phase of
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31 333 increased habitat heterogeneity. Estimated MAP ranges from 765 to 992 mm/yr, whereas
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33 334 estimated MAT is 20.3 °C (Table 1). The biomes of phase II would be in the domains of
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35 335 tropical seasonal forest/savanna and subtropical desert [50] (Fig. S4). In the light of the fauna
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37 336 recorded at ACM [15], we consider the latter inference as unrealistic and most likely
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39 337 attributable to a preservational bias towards drier ecosystems [55]. Alternatively, higher CO₂
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41 338 levels during the Miocene might produce a similar bias in biome reconstructions, given their
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43 339 documented relationship not only with higher temperatures but also enhanced water-use
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45 340 efficiency and leaf-level productivity [56]. This ‘forest fertilization effect’, resulting from
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47 341 higher CO₂ levels in the Miocene, might have resulted in more forested environments than
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49 342 indicated by estimated MAP and TAP based on current standards. Discerning whether such
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51 343 potential biases apply uniformly to the whole ACM sequence would require a taxonomically
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53 344 broader isotopic sampling in selected ACM localities—as averaging values from multiple
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55 345 taxa from the same locality would arguably provide more robust MAP estimates [55].
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57 346 Nevertheless, we consider that the palaeoenvironmental changes recorded by *Micromeryx*
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7 347 isotopic values through time are at least valid in relative terms, even if their exact
8 348 interpretation in terms of extant biomes should be subject to further scrutiny. The
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10 349 development of mosaic environments (with the earlier forested habitats containing for the first
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12 350 time partial clearing as new open patches) in ACM might have allowed the local evolution of
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14 351 new *Micromeryx* morphotypes (i.e., species) adapted to more open landscapes and with
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16 352 different dietary preferences (e.g., more abrasive forbs, shrubs and other ligneous vegetation
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18 353 rich in phytoliths, and even some grass). Such an interpretation is reinforced by the record at
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20 354 ACM/C3-Ak of the bovid *Tethytragus*, a common faunal element in the more open and arid
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22 355 palaeoenvironments from inner Iberia that is otherwise not documented from the Vallès-
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24 356 Penedès Basin [57]. Our results support greater habitat heterogeneity, rather than a complete
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26 357 change in the palaeoenvironment compared to the previous phase. On the one hand,
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28 358 *Micromeryx* morphotype 2 (with affinity for humid conditions) persists in phase II with little
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30 359 variation in MS and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ —with higher values at the end of phase II (at ACM/C4-C1, 11.81
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32 360 Ma) likely indicating that more abrasive foods and/or some grit loaded foliage was eaten at
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34 361 this time. On the other hand, the new morphotypes 1 and 3 appear for the first time with
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36 362 higher mean MS and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 3b, c).

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38 363 These changes toward habitat (canopy) fragmentation, leading to a mosaic of forest
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40 364 patches interrupted by more open woodlands and maybe even shrublands, would have
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42 365 represented a challenge for the frugivorous and presumably arboreal great apes from ACM—
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44 366 especially in dietary terms (given the impossibility of maintaining a year-round supply of ripe
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46 367 fruits), and perhaps also from a locomotor viewpoint (at least for the highly arboreal
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48 368 *Pierolapithecus*, given the need to travel across the canopy to exploit such resources).
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50 369 Admittedly, arboreal adaptations are only unambiguously recorded for the orthograde
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52 370 *Pierolapithecus* [10,33,53,54], while there are no postcranials for *Anoiapithecus*, and
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54 371 *Dryopithecus* appears to have been more pronograde [58]. Nevertheless, there are no
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56 372 indications that *Dryopithecus* was particularly adapted to terrestrial locomotion [58], whereas
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58 373 in contrast *Pliopithecus* has been inferred as a generalised semiarboreal quadruped [59,60],
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7 374 which would have allowed the latter genus to better exploit not only the shrub level but also
8 375 to walk terrestrially among different arboreal feeding sources. Furthermore, the smaller body
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10 376 size of pliopithecoids would have likely allowed them to exploit smaller patches of fruiting
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12 377 trees than in the case of great apes. Overall, the inferred palaeoenvironmental changes might
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14 378 explain why great apes became even rarer faunal elements and were eventually replaced by
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16 379 pliopithecoids during this phase. Our results therefore differ from those of previous analyses
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18 380 based on hypsodonty [4], according to which pliopithecoids generally inhabited more humid
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20 381 environments than hominoids. This discrepancy is largely attributable to the different
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22 382 methods used, ~~as our analysis is performed at a much higher temporal resolution, but for a~~
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24 383 ~~more restricted geographical area and time span.~~ The work by Sukselainen et al. [4] was
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26 384 devised to detect general patterns over broader geographical (all Eurasia) and temporal (~~as~~
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28 385 ~~they considered~~ most of the Miocene) scales than our study, which is designed to test such
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30 386 patterns in a ~~local small region succession, considering with~~ a shorter time span (ca. 1 Myr)
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32 387 but with ~~a~~ considerably higher temporal resolution. The environmental constraints affecting
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34 388 the occurrence of the different primate taxa may vary between distant geographic regions and
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36 389 at different time intervals. For example, the findings by Sukselainen et al. [4] are certainly
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38 390 influenced by the inclusion of several hominoid taxa (such as *Kenyapithecus*, *Ankarapithecus*
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40 391 and *Ouranopithecus*) that surely lived in more arid habitats than pliopithecoids [3], which
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42 392 may result in the overestimation of some subtle (but real) differences between hominoids and
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44 393 pliopithecoids. Accordingly, ~~our conclusions cannot be generalised to Miocene European~~
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46 394 ~~primates as a whole. To test this possibility, similar analyses focused on other~~ ~~the pattern~~
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48 395 ~~documented at ACM must not necessarily hold for other species of pliopithecoids and~~
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50 396 hominoid ~~species from elsewhere would be requireds, which would require undertaking~~
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52 397 ~~similar analyses for other localities where both groups co-occur.~~

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54 398 Phase III — Our results provide compelling evidence for a distinct phase towards the top
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56 399 of the ACM sequence (11.70–11.60 Ma), roughly coinciding with the middle to late Miocene
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58 400 boundary. During such a short interval, dryopithecines reappear at 11.65 Ma after a gap of
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60 401 >200 kyr in which only *Pliopithecus* was recorded, and overlap with the small-bodied stem

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7 402 hominoid *Pliobates* (not previously recorded), even coexisting in a particular locality
8 403 (ACM/C5-D1; 11.63 Ma [5]). *Micromeryx* morphotypes yield MS higher on average than in
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10 404 phase II (average MS of 0.32), less sharp and more rounded cusps, and—for the first time in
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12 405 the sequence—low occlusal relief (Table 1, Fig. 3b). *Micromeryx* tooth enamel mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (-
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14 406 11.1 ± 1.2 ‰, VPDB) (Fig. 3c) is also higher. This evidence lends support to increased
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16 407 opening of the canopy, with trees growing in more open conditions or sparser formations. MS
17 408 and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ranges are the widest (up to twice that recorded at any other previous phase) of the
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19 409 sequence, which is consistent with ~~a~~ greater habitat heterogeneity than in phase II. Phase III
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21 410 witnesses the lowest $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values (Table 1, Fig. 3d). Calculated MAP reaches
22
23 411 the lowest values of the three phases ranging from 608 to 901 mm/yr, and estimated MAT is
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25 412 also the lowest inferred with 17.1 °C—which means a drop of 3 °C compared to phase II
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27 413 (Table 1, Fig. 3c, d). All this evidence suggests a woodland/shrubland biome [50] (Fig. S4).
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29 414 Nonetheless, the record of the aquaphilous tragulid *Dorcatherium navi* [61], flying squirrels
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31 415 [62] and arboreal dormice at ACM/C5-D1 indicate that permanent water masses (palustrine
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33 416 areas or streams) and forests were also present in this phase. Accordingly, our results are
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35 417 consistent with more open, mosaic environments in phase III, although they may have been
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37 418 interspersed with restricted gallery forests, which would have provided a denser tree cover
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39 419 and preserved some subtropical plant elements—contrasting with the predominant vegetation
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41 420 of the nearby areas. Such kind of habitats would have probably been suitable for *Pliobates*
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43 421 (whose small body size would have enabled the exploitation of smaller areas of fruiting
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45 422 trees), which displays a mosaic of primitive and derived postcranial features consistent with
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47 423 cautious and eclectic arboreal climbing, and even some degree of suspensory behaviours
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49 424 [11]—as opposed to the more generalised semiterrestrial quadrupedalism of *Pliopithecus*
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51 425 mentioned above. The decrease in estimated MAP and MAT values throughout the three-
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53 426 phased sequence proposed in this study may be tracking the progressive drop in temperatures
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55 427 that took place throughout the middle and late Miocene and that was responsible for biome
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57 428 change in the Iberian Peninsula, from subtropical to drier and more open conditions [48,49].
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430 **The rare co-occurrence of pliopithecoids and hominoids**

431 Combining tooth wear patterns and stable isotope data for the moschid *Micromeryx* allows us
432 to reconstruct for the first time the local palaeoenvironmental changes that took place during
433 the ca. 1 Myr time span recorded by the ACM series and provide insight on the factors
434 underpinning the rare co-occurrence of hominoids and pliopithecoids. Our results
435 conclusively show that ACM habitats significantly changed with the passing of time and that
436 the recorded turnovers in the primate faunal assemblage are correlated with three main
437 successive environmental phases. Humid conditions are only predominantly present during
438 phase I (at the lowermost portion of the sequence, 12.38–11.95 Ma), where most large-bodied
439 and presumably arboreal hominoids are recorded; from then onwards, humid ecosystems are
440 only intermittently present in the area and only the smaller-bodied and presumably
441 semiterrestrial pliopithecoids are recorded during phase II. Hominoid-bearing localities thus
442 emerge as different from those recording pliopithecoids, with the former corresponding to
443 quite homogeneous habitats with high humidity and continuous canopies (i.e., densely-
444 wooded environments). In contrast, pliopithecoid-bearing localities correspond to less humid
445 and more patchy habitats with a reduced canopy cover. Dryopithecines are recorded again,
446 together with the small-bodied arboreal hominoid *Pliobates*, during the third phase
447 (corresponding to the uppermost portion of the sequence; 11.70–11.60 Ma), characterised by
448 more open conditions and increased environmental heterogeneity. This might be explained by
449 the existence of narrow forest settings (with more humid conditions than its surroundings), to
450 which hominoids would have probably been restricted to a large extent.

451

452 **Conclusions**

453 Our results indicate that the chronostratigraphic distribution of pliopithecoids and hominoids,
454 as previously suspected [1,4,5], is not merely attributable to sampling biases, as the various
455 primate taxa are consistently present in different types of environments. The purported
456 preference of pliopithecoids for more humid environments as compared to large-bodied

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7 457 hominoids, previously inferred based on hypsodonty data [4] is not supported in the case of
8 458 ACM. More generally, our results clearly show that hominoid and pliopithecoids exploited
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10 459 different environments, and support that they displayed differences in behavioural ecology,
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12 460 largely ‘tracking’ the most suitable habitats for each group—which would explain why they
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14 461 only co-occurred at a few localities throughout the European Miocene. Our results further
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16 462 support the view that ACM hominoids, like other Miocene apes as a whole, inhabited more
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18 463 seasonal and arid environments than extant apes [3]. Indeed, isotopic data for the Siwaliks
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20 464 (Pakistan) based on some particular herbivorous mammals (not including *Micromeryx*)
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22 465 [63,64] and rodents show higher $d^{13}C$ values than those of the Vallès-Penedès [65], which
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24 466 evidences that *Sivapithecus*, which is present at some of those sites, might have inhabited
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26 467 ~~even~~ somewhat drier environments. However, given the the potential biases of the record,
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28 468 additional mesowear and isotopic analyses comprising a wider array of taxa would be
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30 469 required to provide more refined palaeoenvironmental reconstructions for specific ACM
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32 470 localities.
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34 471 Furthermore, the results of our study illustrate that continuous and densely-sampled
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36 472 fossiliferous sequences, such as that from ACM, are essential for deciphering the complex
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38 473 interplay between biotic and abiotic factors that shape the chronostratigraphic and geographic
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40 474 distribution patterns of past taxa. Even if local, such sequences enable removing potential
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42 475 biases caused by differences in geographical situation as well as local physiographic and
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44 476 climatic factors among localities in continental-wide studies. In other words, densely-sampled
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46 477 sequences ~~enable permit to detailed~~ focus ~~exclusively~~ on the temporal component of
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48 478 palaeoenvironmental change and, hence, arguably have a greater potential to test hypotheses
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50 479 on the correlation between faunal, climate and habitat change at a much finer scale than ~~some~~
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52 480 ~~other~~ studies at a more global scale. Extending such local comparisons to other densely-
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54 481 sampled sequences covering similar time spans elsewhere in Eurasia would be the logical
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56 482 next step to further investigate the general validity of the conclusions drawn in this paper for
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58 483 the rare co-occurrence of hominoids and pliopithecoids as a whole.
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7 485 **Material and methods**

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9 486 **Hypothesis-testing framework**

10 487 We proceed with the null hypothesis that the chronostratigraphic distribution of
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12 488 pliopithecoids and hominoids through ACM is random relative to the palaeoenvironmental
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14 489 conditions inferred from the associated fauna. If the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, it
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16 490 would follow that hominoids and pliopithecoids might have exploited the same (even if
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18 491 varied) habitats and, hence, the possibility that their rare co-occurrence is merely a statistical
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20 492 artifact due to insufficient sampling could not be discounted. If the null hypothesis is rejected,
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22 493 because one group is consistently recorded in different types of environments, then it would
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24 494 follow that their rare co-occurrence is likely attributable to different ecological preferences.
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26 496 **Data set and ACM stratigraphic series**

27 497 *Micromeryx* (Supplementary Note 1, Fig. S1) specimens analysed in this paper are housed in
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29 498 the Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP) in Sabadell (Spain). They come
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31 499 from 11 fossil localities in the 250 m-thick ACM composite stratigraphic sequence [5,15], in
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33 500 els Hostalets de Pierola (Vallès-Penedès Basin, Catalonia, Spain; Fig. 1a-c). These localities
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35 501 are restricted areas corresponding to a single layer (or stratigraphic horizon), usually between
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37 502 0.2 and 1.0 m in thickness, from which fossil remains were collected (see Alba et al. [5] for
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39 503 further details). The sequence includes more than 200 micro- and/or macromammal localities
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41 504 and spans more than 1 Myr (12.6 to 11.4 Ma; late Aragonian, middle to late Miocene,
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43 505 MN7+8) [5]. The genus *Micromeryx*, widely dispersed across Europe and ubiquitous [18], is
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45 506 common throughout the whole ACM sequence, thus allowing for a stratigraphically
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47 507 continuous sampling. The oldest occurrence of *Micromeryx* sp. in the sequence corresponds
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49 508 to the locality ACM/C1-Ee, with an estimated age of 12.38 Ma, whereas the youngest
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51 509 occurrence corresponds to ACM/C5-D1 (11.63 Ma) (Fig. 1c). The remaining investigated
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53 510 ACM localities cluster in an interval spanning from 11.68 to 12.23 Ma (Fig. 1c). We analyse
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55 511 patterns of tooth wear and enamel stable isotope composition—including carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and
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7 512 oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$)—of three different *Micromeryx* morphotypes (termed
8 513 morphotype 1, 2 and 3). They represent three distinct species, although we refrain from
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10 514 formally naming them (see more details in Supplementary Note 1, Figs. S2 and S3).

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12 515 The use of a single moscid genus in palaeoecological analysis constitutes a novelty of
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14 516 this study, as this group has not previously been explored from the standpoint of mesowear
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16 517 and stable isotopes in tandem, due to the small size of its teeth and the consequent difficulty
17 518 in gathering the data. ~~When inferring palaeoenvironmental change through time (in relation to~~
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19 519 ~~temporal changes in the composition of the primate assemblage), focusing the study on~~
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21 520 ~~*Micromeryx* allows minimising the biases that would be introduced by analysing a wider~~
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23 521 ~~array of taxa, which are much less ubiquitously and continuously recorded across the ACM~~
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25 522 ~~sequence. Indeed, adding more taxa could contribute to refine palaeoenvironmental~~
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27 523 ~~reconstruction for particular sites and stratigraphic bins, but would also introduce biases~~
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29 524 ~~caused by the sparser record of less abundant taxa along the ACM sequence.~~ Combining both
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31 525 approaches allows us to make robust inferences not only about the feeding ecology of
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33 526 *Micromeryx*, but also ~~to~~ in estimating climatic and environmental parameters through the
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35 527 ACM sequence. Mesowear and stable isotopes represent different time spans of the animal's
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37 528 life and operate over different temporal scales—with the former recording an average of the
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39 529 diet during the last years before death [24,66] and the latter corresponding to the time period
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41 530 of tooth mineralisation, which usually records earlier years of the animal's ontogeny [67].

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43 531 When inferring palaeoenvironmental change through time (in relation to temporal changes in
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45 532 the composition of the primate assemblage), focusing the study on *Micromeryx* minimises the
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47 533 biases that would be introduced by analysing a wider array of taxa, which are much less
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49 534 ubiquitously and continuously recorded across the ACM sequence. Indeed, adding more taxa
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51 535 could contribute to refining palaeoenvironmental reconstructions for particular sites and
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53 536 stratigraphic bins, but it would also introduce biases caused by the sparser record of less
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55 537 abundant taxa along the ACM sequence

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539 **Long-term patterns of tooth mesowear**

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7 540 Mesowear is a method for determining diet (browse vs. graze) and abrasiveness of foods and
8 541 exogenous items based on gross dental wear [25]. It provides an immediate long-term dietary
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10 542 signal compared to the individual's lifespan and is a very powerful tool for documenting
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12 543 changes in fossil habitats and climate [26,51]. Mesowear for 45 teeth, each one belonging to a
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14 544 different individual, was recorded. The young and old-adult individuals were identified by
15 545 dental wear and discarded from analyses [68]. Preference was given to upper cheek teeth
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17 546 (usually second molars) but lower teeth were also evaluated when necessary following Fraser
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19 547 et al. [69]. Individual cusp shape and occlusal relief were scored on the buccal cups. Cusp
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21 548 shape was categorised as either sharp = pS, rounded = pR, or blunt = pB, according to the
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23 549 degree of facet development. Occlusal relief was categorised as high = pH or low= pL,
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25 550 depending on the relative difference in height between the tip of the cusp and the intercuspal
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27 551 valley. A mesowear score (MS) for each ACM locality was obtained in order to trace
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29 552 temporal evolution following a five-point scoring system [70]: 0 = high relief and sharp
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31 553 cusps; 1 = high relief and rounded cusps; 2 = low relief and rounded cusps; 2.5 = low relief
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33 554 and sharp cusps; and 3 = low relief and blunt cusps. We do not use the more recent scoring
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35 555 system by Muhlbachler et al. [71] because it was specifically devised for the analysis of equid
36
37 556 mesowear. Although the method could potentially work with other taxa, we prefer to rely on
38
39 557 the scoring system [70] customarily used to score ruminant mesowear. See Supplementary
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41 558 Note 2 for further details on this method.

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43 560 **Stable isotope analysis**

44 561 Stable carbon and oxygen isotope compositions ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of mammalian tooth enamel
45 562 reflect diet, primary production, as well as animal and landscape water use, which permit to
46 563 reconstruct palaeoecological preferences and, in turn, past environmental and climatic
47 564 conditions [23,67,72,73]. For herbivorous terrestrial mammals, tooth enamel $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values are
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49 565 largely controlled by the photosynthetic pathway followed by the ingested plants, ~~and~~ as well
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51 566 as by plant water economy, and informs about the vegetation cover present in an area [74].

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53 567 The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of mammalian bioapatite—both the carbonate fraction ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$) and the

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7 568 phosphate fraction ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$)—record the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of body water, which in turn reflects the
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9 569 fluxes and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of oxygen entering and exiting the body. Within an obligate-drinking
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11 570 taxon, variations in body water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values can be interpreted as chiefly reflecting changes in
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13 571 the isotopic composition of ingested water, which varies with mean annual temperature and
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15 572 aridity [23,67,72,73].

16 573 A total of 37 samples were analysed for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$, whereas 30 tooth enamel
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18 574 samples were analysed for $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$. Tooth enamel was sampled using a rotary drill with a
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20 575 diamond-tipped dental burr under a microscope to recover enamel from an area of the tooth as
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22 576 large as possible to avoid seasonal bias in the time of mineralisation. Sampling protocol and
23
24 577 chemical treatment follows Domingo et al. [23] for carbonate and phosphate in bioapatite.

25 578 When performing isotopic analyses on fossil material, diagenetic effects must be
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27 579 addressed before attempting to extract palaeoecological, palaeoenvironmental and/or
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29 580 palaeoclimatic information. When both $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ values have been determined,
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31 581 post mortem alteration can be checked by calculating the difference between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and
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33 582 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ ($\Delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3\text{-PO}_4} = \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3} - \delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$). This follows the premise that bioapatite in modern
34
35 583 mammals have a narrow-restricted difference of ~8.6–9.1‰ [21,22]. $\Delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3\text{-PO}_4}$ mean value
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37 584 for the whole dataset of *Micromeryx* samples is $8.6 \pm 0.8\text{‰}$, and therefore it is within the
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39 585 expected range for unaltered bioapatite.

40 586 Mean Annual Precipitation (MAP) from *Micromeryx* tooth enamel $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was estimated
41
42 587 following Kohn [55], both with and without altitude and latitude correction. Estimated Mean
43
44 588 Annual Temperature (MAT) was also calculated following a two-stepped method and using
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46 589 published equations [75,76]. See Supplementary Notes 3 and 4 for a full description of
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48 590 sample processing and and chemical treatment, and estimated MAP and MAT calculations.

49 592 **Statistical analyses**

50 593 Chi-square (χ^2) and Fisher's exact tests with level of significance $p < 0.05$ were performed
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52 594 based on individual mesowear score for testing for significant differences in mesowear
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7 595 between the three *Micromeryx* morphotypes. Shapiro-Wilk tests and Q-Q plots revealed
8 596 normal distributions for isotopic data. Parametric analysis of variance (ANOVA) and
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10 597 Turkey's post hoc pairwise comparisons were performed to test for significant mean
11
12 598 differences at $p < 0.05$ between all possible pairs using a Studentised range distribution.
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14 599 Locally weighted polynomial lines were fitted to the isotopic data. Calculations for isotopic
15 600 data further include a 95 % confidence region. Descriptive and inferential statistics were
16
17 601 conducted using R software version 3.5.1.
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19 602
20 603 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**
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22 604 Not applicable
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24 605
25 606 **Consent for publication**
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27 607 Not applicable
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31 609 **Availability of data and materials**
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33 610 All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article [and its
34
35 611 supplementary information files].
36
37 612
38 613 **Competing interests**
39
40 614 The authors declare no competing interests.
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622 groups “Neogene and Quaternary Vertebrate Paleobiodiversity (NQVP)” (2017 SGR 116
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627

628 **Authors' contributions**

629 D.D.M. and D.M.A. designed the study; D.D.M. and L.D. collected and analysed the main
630 data, while I.C.V., I.M.S. and J.M.R. provided additional contextual data; D.D.M., L.D.,
631 I.C.V. and D.M.A. interpreted the data, with input from the remaining authors; D.D.M.,
632 D.M.A. and L.D. drafted and wrote the paper. [All authors read and approved the final](#)
633 [manuscript.](#)
634

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32 832 **Figure captions**

33 833 **Figure 1. Abocador de Can Mata (ACM) and the moschid *Micromeryx*.** **a** Geographical
34 834 situation and general geological context of the Vallès-Penedès Basin. **b** Detailed geological
35 835 map of the basin and the sequence of Abocador de Can Mata (ACM) (black dot). **c**
36 836 Correlation of the composite local magnetostratigraphy of ACM series with the Geomagnetic
37 837 Polarity Time Scale (modified from Alba et al. [5]). European Land Mammal Ages, Mammal
38 838 Neogene (MN) units and local biozones of the Vallès-Penedès Basin are shown on the left.
39 839 The shadowed region indicates an unsampled interval of the Vallès-Penedès record. The
40 840 stratigraphic positions of the ACM localities studied in this work are shown to the right on the
41 841 composite lithostratigraphic column. Note that the bottom boundary of the lowermost local
42 842 biozone is unknown. **d** Life reconstruction of a *Micromeryx azanzae* male. Art by I.M.S.
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7 844 **Figure 2. Scatter plot of mesowear and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (‰ VPDB) of *Micromeryx*.** Stippled
8 845 areas show the transition between C_3 -dominated diets, mixed C_3 - C_4 diets, and C_4 -dominated
9 846 diets. Colour informs about *Micromeryx* morphotype (green for *Micromeryx* morphotype 1,
10 847 blue for *Micromeryx* morphotype 2 and yellow for *Micromeryx* morphotype 3) and symbol
11 848 refers to the temporal range within the sedimentary sequence (diamond for 12.38–11.95 Ma,
12 849 circle for 11.90–11.79 Ma and square for 11.70–11.60 Ma). See Supplementary Notes 2 and 3
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17 850 for further details.

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20 852 **Figure 3. Correlation of mesowear and isotopic values of *Micromeryx* arranged**
21 853 **temporally along the ACM sequence. a** Environmental phases, separated by dashed lines,
22 854 here detected and stratigraphic ranges of the primates recovered at ACM based on their
23 855 occurrences in the localities. **b** Average mesowear scores (MS) by locality for *Micromeryx*
24 856 morphotypes. **c** *Micromeryx* tooth enamel raw and mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB). Calculated average
25 857 modern equivalent of diet composition ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{diet, meq}}$, ‰ VPDB) and estimated MAP (mm/yr)
26 858 values (without [MAP^a] and with [MAP^b] altitude and latitude correction) are given in
27 859 parentheses. **d** *Micromeryx* tooth enamel raw and mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ (‰ VSMOW)
28 860 values. Calculated MAT (°C) values are given in parentheses. Locally weighted polynomial
29 861 lines are fitted to isotopic data. Calculations further include the 95% confidence region.
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34 862 Colour symbols are for raw data and grey symbols are for mean values. See Supplementary
35 863 Note 4 for further details.

36 864 **Additional Information**

37 865 -Additional file 1: Supplementary Information. Additional information on the moschid

38 866 *Micromeryx*, tooth-wear patterns and stable isotope analysis. (.word)

39 867 -Additional file 2: Fig. S1. *Moschus* and *Micromeryx*. A *Moschus moschiferus* adult male.

40 868 Image by Vladimir Prikhod'ko, reproduced with permission of the author. B Skull of *M.*

41 869 *moschiferus* showing the enlarged upper canines of males. C MPZ 2006/413, skull of a

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7 §72 [juvenile male *Micromeryx azanzae* from Toril-3 \(middle Miocene, MN7+8, Zaragoza, Spain\).](#)
8 §73 [D Life reconstruction of a *Micromeryx* male. Art by Mauricio Antón, reproduced with](#)
9 [permission of the author. \(.pdf\)](#)
10 §74
11 §75
12 §76 [-Additional file 3: Fig. S2. ACM *Micromeryx*, examples of the lower dentition of the](#)
13 [morphotypes with remarks on their most conspicuous features. A Morphotype 1, specimens](#)
14 [IPS90767 and IPS43689. B Morphotype 2, specimen IPS44457. C Morphotype 3, specimens](#)
15 [IPS43907 and IPS57264. \(.pdf\)](#)
16 §77
17 §78
18 §79
19 §80
20 §81 [-Additional file 4: Fig. S3. ACM *Micromeryx*, examples of the upper dentition of the](#)
21 [morphotypes with remarks on their most conspicuous features. A Morphotype 1, specimens](#)
22 [IPS44358 and IPS45524. B Morphotype 2, specimens IPS45552, IPS48103 and IPS29766. C](#)
23 [Morphotype 3, specimen IPS45382. Anatomical definitions: protocone-T, T-shaped fold of](#)
24 [enamel formed at the terminal end of the post-protocrista; metaconule-T, T-shaped fold of](#)
25 [enamel formed at the terminal end of the pre-metaconulecrista. \(.pdf\)](#)
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31 §87
32 §88 [-Additional file 5: Fig. S4. Whittaker's biome classification plot showing terrestrial biome-](#)
33 [types as function of mean annual precipitation \(MAP; in cm\) and temperature \(MAT; in °C\).](#)
34 §89 [ACM localities from the three distinct environmental phases are plotted according to](#)
35 [calculated values of estimated MAP and MAT using average stable carbon and oxygen](#)
36 [isotope values of *Micromeryx* enamel apatite. For each locality we show estimated MAP](#)
37 [before \(circles\) and after \(squares\) correcting for palaeolatitude and palaeoaltitude. Note that](#)
38 [these corrections result in lower estimates. Diagram modified from Whittaker \[42\]. \(.pdf\)](#)
39 §90
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45 §96 [-Additional file 6: Table S1. Individual values of mesowear and stable isotopes of](#)
46 [Morphotype 1, specimens](#)
47 [Morphotype 2, specimens](#)
48 [Morphotype 3, specimen](#)
49 [IPS90767 and IPS43689. \(.pdf\)](#)
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-Additional file 7: Table S2. ANOVA and Tukey post hoc tests for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰ VPDB), $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CO}_3}$ (‰ VSMOW), and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PO}_4}$ (‰ VSMOW) values of *Micromeryx* from Abocador de Can Mata according to morphotypes and environmental phases. Values in bold are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). (.pdf)

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27 **Tables**

28 **Table 1. Summary of mesowear and isotopic values of *Micromeryx* from the ACM sequence according to morphotypes and environmental phases.**

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Morphotypes	# M	pS	pR	pH	M S	#C	$\delta^{13}C$	SD $\delta^{13}C$	$\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$	SD $\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$	#P	$\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$	SD $\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{18}O_{CO_3} - \delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$
Morphotype 1	8	69.2	30.8	10.0	0.31	8	-10.5	0.7	27.9	1.0	6	19.6	1.4	8.4
Morphotype 2	24	80.6	19.4	10.0	0.19	21	-11.8	0.8	27.7	1.5	19	19.1	1.9	8.7
Morphotype 3	11	86.7	13.3	95.0	0.21	6	-11.0	1.2	27.0	0.6	5	18.5	1.1	8.3

Environmental phases	# M	pS	pR	pH	M S	# C	$\delta^{13}C$	SD $\delta^{13}C$	$\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$	SD $\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$	# P	$\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$	SD $\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$	$\Delta \delta^{18}O_{CO_3} - \delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$	$\delta^{13}C_{diet, mequ}$	MAP ^a (mm/yr)	MAP ^b (mm/yr)	MAT (°C)
Phase III (11.70–11.60 Ma)	23	71.9	28.1	97.3	0.32	19	-11.1	1.2	27.2	1.2	19	18.5	1.6	8.7	-27.2	801	608	17.1
Phase II (11.90–11.79 Ma)	15	83.3	16.7	10.0	0.16	13	-11.4	1.2	27.7	1.2	6	19.8	1.7	8.2	-27.5	992	765	20.3
Phase I (12.33–11.95 Ma)	7	90.9	9.1	10.0	0.09	5	-12.0	0.3	28.9	0.8	5	20.4	0.9	8.5	-28.1	1190	928	21.8

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39 #M (number of samples for mesowear); percentage of specimens with sharp (pS), and rounded (pR) cusps; percentage of specimens with high (pH) occlusal
40 relief; mesowear score (MS); #C (number of samples for stable isotope analyses on the carbonate fraction); mean $\delta^{13}C$ (‰ VPDB); standard deviation (SD)
41 $\delta^{13}C$ (‰ VPDB); mean $\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$ (‰ VSMOW); standard deviation (SD) $\delta^{18}O_{CO_3}$ (‰ VSMOW); #P (number of samples for stable isotope analyses on the
42 phosphate fraction); mean $\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$ (‰ VSMOW); standard deviation (SD) $\delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$ (‰ VSMOW); $\Delta \delta^{18}O_{CO_3} - \delta^{18}O_{PO_4}$, mean $\delta^{13}C_{diet, mequ}$ (‰ VPDB); inferred
43 mean MAP (mm/yr) (from Kohn [54]) without (estimated MAP^a) and with (estimated MAP^b) altitude and latitude correction; and inferred mean MAT (°C).
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Dear Dr. Vitor Sousa,

We submit a new revised version of our manuscript MS# BMCB-D-20-00663R1 entitled "Palaeoecological differences underlie rare co-occurrence of Miocene European primates", by DeMiguel and co-authors, to be considered for publication in BMC Biology.

We are very grateful to the Editor and the reviewers for their suggestions and constructive comments on the previous versions of this paper, which we think have helped to significantly improve the manuscript. We have accepted all the final suggestions made by Reviewers 3 and 4. Below, we have explained point-by-point how we have dealt with the reviewers' comments.

We hope that our manuscript will be considered suitable for the journal. We prepared the manuscript by strictly adhering to the BMC Biology submission guidelines.

Yours sincerely,

Daniel DeMiguel

ARAID / University of Zaragoza

Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont

BMCB-D-20-00663R1

Understanding the rare co-occurrence of Miocene European primates based on musk-deer evolutionary palaeoecology

Daniel DeMiguel; Laura Domingo; Israel M. Sánchez; Isaac Casanovas-Vilar; Josep M. Robles; David M. Alba

Dear Dr. DeMiguel,

I'm writing to thank you for submitting your revised manuscript which has now been seen by the referees that originally reviewed it, whose comments you will find below. In light of what they have to say, I am pleased to let you know that we shall be happy in principle to accept the manuscript for publication in BMC Biology, subject to some minor revision.

You will note that Reviewers 3 and 4 have made suggestions of points that should be clarified in the manuscript, which we ask you to follow.

You should ensure that your article complies with our Minimum Standards of Reporting checklist - <http://resource-cms.springernature.com/springer-cms/rest/v1/content/7117202/data/v2/Minimum+standards+of+reporting+checklist> . For instance:

- For the figures and additional files, please indicated the number of replicates in the legends where applicable. Where $n < 6$, the individual data values should be provided and cited clearly – for the Figures and Additional files please ensure a file providing individual data values is cited in the figure legend. Supporting data values should be included in an additional excel file, and also referred to in the 'Availability of Data and Materials'.

I would also like to ask you to ensure that your revised manuscript conforms to the journal style and that it includes all the necessary sections. Formatting guidelines for all article types can be found in the Instructions for Authors at <https://bmcbiol.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript>. It is important that your files are correctly formatted, to avoid unnecessary delays in the production process in the event of publication. You will have to make the following changes:

- Manuscripts should have the following subsections: Background/Results/Discussion/Conclusions/Methods. Please change the heading 'Materials and Methods' to 'Methods';

Done. We have used "Methods" instead of "Materials and Methods".

- You should upload your figures as separate files; Figures should be uploaded as high-resolution files in the appropriate format (e.g. TIFF, PDF, JPEG, EPS);

Ok. We will submit figures as separate files in TIFF.

- **You should upload your additional files as separate files;**

Ok. We will upload additional files as separate files.

- **Additional files should be uploaded as a “Supplementary” file type in the system;**

Ok. We will upload additional files as a "Supplementary" file type.

- **Please rename supplementary files as ‘Additional file X’, and cite explicitly by additional file name in the manuscript e.g. ‘Additional file 1: Fig. S1; Additional file 2: Fig. S2; Additional file Y: Movie X; ...’. Please ensure that if you have more than one file and additional files that they are cited in ascending order within the main body of text;**

Done.

- **Please provide a subsection just after the main file legends listing all the additional files and include: file name (e.g. Additional File 1: Fig. S1), title and short description of data, file format including the correct file extension (for example .pdf, .xls, .txt, .ppt);**

Done.

- **Please move all references to the main reference list (i.e. no additional references in Additional Files). These should be included in the main text when the Additional File is first introduced, for example “...see Additional File 1: Table S1) [XX-XX]”; please ensure the reference list is numbered in the order as they appear in the text;**

As explained below, there are some extra notes in the Additional file 1 ("Supplementary Information") that contain a few references. Accordingly, we think that these references are more suitable to be at the end of the Additional file 1 (and not in the main text in where they do not appear) in order to be more accesible to the readers. Nevertheless, if the AE considers that this does not match so well with the journal's style, we would consider his recommendation and move them to the main text.

- **All descriptions of methods and results should be included in the main ‘Methods’ and ‘Results’ sections; please move information currently in the Additional file to the main ‘Methods’ and ‘Results’ sections, and ensure to update any references in the main text body;**

As we have specified in a message with the AE, and he agrees, what we have adhered to the Supplementary Information file is only complementary (and not strictly necessary) explanation of some methodological concerns (particularlry regarding original formulas from other authors for MAP and MAT calculation). So, we leave it as currently is.

- **The “Authors’ Contributions” section of the Declarations should include the text “All authors read and approved the final manuscript”.**

Done. All the points above mentioned by the AE have been taken into account, and the manuscript has been reviewed accordingly.

I have also read the manuscript with our journal style in mind and have slightly tweaked the title to provide a clearer focus on the major advances of the paper. Would you be fine with this title, and confirm its scientific accuracy?

Proposed Title:

" Differences in behavioral ecology underlie rare co-occurrence of Miocene European primates"

We are most grateful to the AE for this title proposal, as we agree it is more suitable as the previous title. Nevertheless, if possible, we would prefer to use the term "palaeoecological differences" instead of "behavioural ecology", since it appears to us more suitable given the content of our manuscript. Accordingly, in the revised manuscript we have changed the title as "Palaeoecological differences underlie rare co-occurrence of Miocene European primates". If the AE considers that our proposal does not match so well with the journal's style, we would be happy to use the title proposed by the AE.

I would also ask that you revise the abstract in line with the suggestion from Reviewer 4.

Done. We have rephrased the abstract in line with the reviewer's suggestions.

Finally, to proceed with publication we require confirmation of authorship from all co-authors. We have not yet received a response from the following authors:

Israel M. Sánchez (israel.sanchez@icp.cat)

Isaac Casanovas-Vilar (isaac.casanovas@icp.cat)

I have resent the verification email containing the confirmation link. May I kindly ask that you follow up on this with the co-author or provide us with an alternative email address, if necessary? They should contact us directly to confirm co-authorship if they have any problems.

Done. We have contacted the editorial office and both authors have confirmed their co-authorship.

If any of the authors wishes to display their twitter handle in the published paper, please provide them next to the authors' names in the Authors' Information section of the manuscript.

At this stage, authors are welcome to submit an image highlighting their research for display on our webpage and social media. Images should be high resolution, free from copyright, in a TIFF, JPEG or PDF format, and they should not be overlaid with graphics or drawings. Please note that we cannot guarantee the display of images, as the editors will make the

final selection. Please send your images to our editorial inbox at bmcbiologyeditorial@biomedcentral.com.

We thank the AE for inviting us to submit an image linked with our research. We will consider this, and if all co-authors agree and we can prepare a suitable image, we will send it to the editorial inbox.

We shall hope to see your revised manuscript by 11 Dec 2020 . If you think it is likely to take longer to prepare, please give us some estimate of when we can expect it, to avoid inappropriate reminders.

You should upload your cover letter and revised manuscript through <https://www.editorialmanager.com/bmcb/>.

Please don't hesitate to get in touch if you have any questions.

Kind regards,

Vitor

Vitor Sousa, PhD
Associate Editor, BMC Biology
<https://bmcbiol.biomedcentral.com/>

Reviewer #3: I want to begin by acknowledging the tremendous work of the authors in responding so carefully and constructively to the comments of five reviewers. I also thank the editors at BMC Biology, particularly Dr. Vitor Sousa, for a clear and concise synthesis of reviewer comments. As a reviewer, I found it very helpful.

I think that the authors have addressed the major points and concerns of the reviewers and have improved the paper. I strongly recommend this paper for publication.

I have a few comments and suggestions that I have divided into two groups. The first group, the more important of the two, includes some comments and minor clarifications. The second group consists of minor language suggestions.

Group 1:

II. 194-195: This reviewer is confused by the following: "which appear strictly frugivorous, albeit with a different degree of frugivory" Is the intent a different type of frugivory? Please clarify.

Here we have merely referred to the fact that *Micromeryx flourensianus* from Rudabánya fed mostly on fruits but with some of seasonal alternance for other components (as showed by differences in temporal resolution between meso- and micro-wear found by Merceron et al. 2007). Nevertheless, and because it does not provide relevant information to the aim of this

particular paragraph, we have removed the confused statement "albeit with a different degree of frugivory".

II. 266-269: Please make it clear that these are estimated mean annual precipitation values here and throughout the paper. Model on which these are derived has produced estimated MAP here and elsewhere that are hard to reconcile with other climate indicators.

Done. We have corrected this by adding "the estimated". Now the sentence is "However, a drop in the estimated Mean Annual Precipitation (MAP) values". Following also the reviewer's suggestion, we have checked this throughout the paper.

II. 269-270: Not for this paper but perhaps a factor could be proportion of asynchronous v synchronous fruiting. Synchronous fruiting would advantage terrestrial foragers more than asynchronous fruiting. Something to ruminare on...

We appreciate this interesting comment by the reviewer, and we will take it into account for our future work on the topic.

II. 329-332: Were these lines to be deleted? Following lines are repetitive, not sure which are favored by authors. This reviewer recommends following lines.

Yes, it was an error, and these lines should have been deleted from the former version of the manuscript. Following the comment by the reviewer, we have deleted them now, and merely used to the following lines.

I. 432: ranges are the greatest (up to ??) - twice what? up to twice that recorded at any other locality in the sequence?

Done. We have been more clear in this regard by using "up to twice that recorded at any other previous phase".

II. 487-491: Recommend against introducing comparison to Siwaliks in the Conclusion. Could bring into Discussion but I do not see a ready place to do so.

We included this comparison with the Siwaliks in the conclusions following a suggestion by reviewer #4. We acknowledge it might appear a bit out of place, but any other place would probably be less appropriate. Accordingly, no significant changes were introduced in this regard.

II. 563-4 suggestion: The young and old adult individuals were identified by dental wear and discarded from analyses.

Done. We have incorporated this suggestion.

Figure 3 caption: A few suggestions to clarify what is represented in this excellent figure.

I. 891: a Environmental phases, separated by dashed lines, and stratigraphic ranges of the primates recovered at ACM based on occurrence in localities. b Average mesowear scores (MS) by locality for Micromeryx morphotypes. c ... Calculated average modern equivalent of diet ... and MAP...

I. 900 add: (See Supplementary Note 4 for further details.)

Done. We thank the reviewer for all these recommendations.

Supplementary Information:

Figure S4:

In caption please note how values of MAP and MAT were calculated.

Suggestion: ACM localities from the three distinct environmental phases are plotted according to calculated values of MAP and MAT using average stable carbon and oxygen isotope values of Micromeryx enamel apatite.

Done. We appreciate this suggestion by the reviewer.

Group 2:

I. 110 While inhomogeneous is not incorrect, perhaps variable is a better word to use here

II. 116-118: Because the diet of ... with the habitats in which it lives...

I. 118: preferences

I. 149 delete "reported"

I. 159: perhaps, composition can be used to ...

I. 179: is compatible with regular (omit "a")

I. 198: was capable of foraging on fruits, seeds, and soft leaves. [lessens the dichotomy between fruit/seed and browse diet]

I. 260 suggest replacing "progressive" with slight; ...would have led to a slight increase...

I. 264 suggest replacing "entail" with mean

II. 266-7: Perhaps something like, " a drop in the estimated Mean Annual Precipitation

I. 268: latitude

I. 405: (most of the Miocene)

II. 406-7: patterns in a small region with a shorter time span... but with considerably higher....

I. 433: consistent with greater habitat...

I. 434: MAP estimates reach... or Calculated MAP reaches

I. 435: MAP estimates reach the lowest value of...

I. 501: sequences permit detailed focus on the...

I. 503: climate and habitat change at a much finer scale than studies at...

I. 520: stratigraphic series

I. 526: 0.2 and 1.0 m or 0.2 and about 1 m

II 543-549: suggest moving to the end of the paragraph

I. 545 Micromeryx minimizes the biases

I. 547 contribution to refining paleoenvironmental reconstructions... but it would also introduce

I. 551 Micromeryx, but also in estimating climatic and environmental...

I. 585: ingested plants, as well as...

I. 603: mammals has a restricted difference...

I. 607: latitude

Done. We have incorporated all these Group 2 minor language suggestions made by the reviewer.

Reviewer #4: I thank the authors for their time in making these revisions to their manuscript. In particular I am thankful for the many alterations of specific language and the substantial addition to the description of methods found in this latest revision. My principle concern is that the authors need to bring some of the nuance found in the body of their manuscript into the conclusion of their abstract, which at this time still appears to present the findings of this research as a refutation of Sukselainen. As the authors convincingly argue in their manuscript and in response to the concerns of multiple reviewers, the differing findings presented here result in part from a difference in the scale of analysis, on multiple levels. I believe the work presented in this study is very important and should be published, with a number of small changes that I detail below.

Sincerely,

Daniel Green

We are thankful to the reviewer for his constructive comments. We explain in detail below how we have followed all the concerns.

Page 2, conclusion of abstract: the conclusion here lacks the subtlety of the paper overall. In the main text of the manuscript, a geographically and temporally detailed analysis of the ACM is contrasted with a coarser analysis of Eurasian primates in the Miocene. It's important here in the abstract that your text not give the impression that your results simply "contradict" those of Sukselainen: indeed your manuscript and reviewer replies provide convincing explanations for the divergent observations of both approaches. I'd amend the text of your conclusion to highlight the importance of detailed local investigations as a compliment to and comment upon broader approaches.

Ok. Following this recommendation, we have rephrased the last portion of the abstract as follows:

"These results support the view that pliopithecoid primates preferred less humid habitats than hominoids, and reveal that differences in behavioural ecology were the main factor underpinning their rare co-occurrence during the European Miocene. Our findings further support that ACM hominoids, like Miocene apes as a whole, inhabited more seasonal environments than extant apes. Finally, this study highlights the importance of high-resolution, local investigations to complement larger-scale analyses and illustrates that continuous and densely-sampled fossiliferous sequences are essential for deciphering the complex interplay between biotic and abiotic factors that shaped past diversity."

Page 4, lines 40-46: change "Focusing on the accompanying fauna within a single area and

throughout a restricted time span would considerably reduce such potential biases and allow to test..." to "Focusing on fauna that accompany primates within a single area and over a restricted time span would allow us to test..." The reasoning behind my proposed textual change is that a more local analysis will have both advantages and disadvantages compared to a larger regional analysis. Furthermore, in the rest of the paragraph you elaborate on some of the potential gains of a detailed study of the ACM. So, framing this in a positive manner only places you on firmer ground here.

We rephrased this sentence as suggested by the reviewer except that, unless we are mistaken, fauna is singular (plural faunae or faunas) and hence the verb should be "accompanies". We circumvented this problem by using "faunal elements" instead of "fauna":

"Focusing on faunal elements that accompany primates within a single area and over a restricted time span would allow us to test whether turnovers in the primate assemblage are correlated to local changes in palaeoenvironmental conditions."

Page 8, line 198: change "was capable to feed" to "was capable of feeding..."

Done.

Page 11, line 268: change "latitud" to "latitude..."

Done.

Page 11, lines 271-273: please place a space between the number and the permil symbol, per SI guidelines. Also you have omitted the permil symbol for one of your reported numbers. It's worthwhile noting that a decline in $\delta^{18}O$ values would also be consistent with increased fruit rather than leaf consumption: something you might want to mention given the carbon results.

Done.

Page 13, lines 329-332: note that this text needs editing for typos and clarity.

Done. We have removed all this part of the paragraph as it was inadvertently kept from the former version and must be deleted. The following text "This immediately precedes a first short pulse ... more abundant record at 12.0–11.9 [5]." is neatly written in this regard.

Page 16, line 407: the phrase "higher temporal resolution" is used just a few lines earlier and so is repetitious here. Understatement would have a greater effect: I recommend going through this paragraph to make sure content isn't being duplicated.

OK. We have removed reiterative statements from this part of the text, which now reads as follows:

"This discrepancy is largely attributable to the different methods used. The work by Sukselainen et al. [4] was devised to detect general patterns over broader geographical (all Eurasia) and temporal (most of the Miocene) scales than our study, which is designed to test such patterns

in a small region with a shorter time span (ca. 1 Myr) but with considerably higher temporal resolution."

Page 16, line 419-420: please copy edit this sentence: I understand what you're trying to say but the wording can be improved for clarity.

The reviewer refers to the sentence "Accordingly, the pattern documented at ACM must not necessarily hold for other species of pliopithecoids and hominoids, which would require undertaking similar analyses for other localities where both groups co-occur". We rephrased it as follows:

"Accordingly, our conclusions cannot be generalized to Miocene European primates as a whole. To test this possibility, similar analyses focused on other pliopithecoid and hominoid species from elsewhere would be required."

Page 19, line 491: delete the word "even."

Done.

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